

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE BOND BEHAVIOR OF CFRP-TO-STEEL JOINTS UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

This work presents an experimental and numerical investigation of the bond behavior of CFRP-to-steel interfaces under cyclic loading. The composite strip (i.e., CFRP and adhesive) experiences fatigue degradation during cyclic loading, which needs to be properly considered to model debonding failures. In this regard, a numerical approach that separately considers the fatigue behavior of the bonded interface and of the composite is proposed. Experimental results of single-lap direct shear tests are presented and employed to calibrate parameters of the numerical model. A parametric analysis is performed to investigate the effect of the main design parameters on the strengthened system performance.

KEYWORDS

Bond; CFRP-steel joints; fatigue; direct shear test; finite element model; parametric analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Civil metallic structures are sensitive to crack formation and propagation when subjected to cyclic loadings, such as traffic-loads and wind-induced vibrations, which often result in a consequent accumulation of damage that can lead to fatigue failures. In recent years, a growing concern regarding fatigue crack propagation in metallic structures has increased the need of efficient strengthening and repairing techniques in order to avoid possible catastrophic collapses. This issue concerns both the design of new structural elements and the strengthening of existing structural components, which are facing longer service lives and often need reinforcement (Schijve, 2003)(Cruz et al., 2007). Among different approaches available to increase the fatigue performances, the local strengthening is a valid and cost-effective solution, alternative to the more expensive whole replacement of damaged parts. Traditional methods conventionally adopted to strengthen existing metallic structures are based on the application of bolted or welded metallic plates, which however are prone to corrosion and potentially lead to further stress concentrations (Domazet, 1996). As an alternative, the application of externally bonded (EB) fiber reinforced composites on damaged steel structures and in particular of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP), represents an effective solution to restore their bearing capacity or extend their fatigue life. EB CFRP reinforcements, directly bonded to the substrate with specific epoxy-based adhesives, have high strength-to-weight ratio, low invasiveness, do not corrode, and entail for a limited increment of the dead load (Zhao, 2013). Different experimental and numerical studies focused on the fatigue behavior of CFRP-strengthened steel members, showing their effectiveness in reducing crack growth rate and in extending fatigue life (Täljsten et al., 2009)(Ghafoori et al., 2015)(Colombi & Fava, 2015).

In FRP-strengthened structures, a part of the acting load is transferred from the substrate to the composite through shear stress exchange mechanisms occurring at the bonded interface. Existing studies demonstrated that dynamic loads could induce a cohesive debonding in the adhesive layer of CFRP-steel joints, which over time can reduce their bearing capacity (Bocciarelli et al., 2009)(Borrie et al., 2021)(Teng et al., 2012). Extensive research has been conducted on the bond behavior of CFRP-steel joints, mainly focusing on their response under monotonic loading conditions (Xia & Teng, 2005)(Fernando et al., 2014) and different bond-slip models have been proposed to predict the

response of strengthened members (Bocciarelli et al., 2007)(Jiang et al., 2021). Despite the strong influence of cyclic loading on the system response, the knowledge of the fatigue behavior of such bonded interfaces is still rather limited. Indeed, among existing studies, only a few focused on the evaluation of fatigue performances of CFRP-to-steel bonded joints (Liu et al., 2010)(Colombi & Fava, 2012)(Wang et al., 2019)(Doroudi et al., 2019). Within this context, theoretical and numerical studies are even more limited than experimental ones. Cohesive models have been proposed for the investigation of shear-loaded interfaces (Martinelli & Caggiano, 2014)(Carrara & De Lorenzis, 2015)(Doroudi et al., 2020). Within this context, in (Bocciarelli, 2021) a non-linear damaging cohesive law with exponential softening was proposed.

The bond behavior of CFRP-steel joints exhibiting cohesive debonding in the adhesive layer was found to be strongly influenced by the adhesive properties. Particularly, experimental and analytical studies showed that the bond capacity of adhesively-bonded joints was strongly influenced by the adhesive fracture energy, i.e., the area below the bond-slip curve (Yu et al., 2012). Standard epoxy adhesives, usually employed to bond CFRP plates, are generally characterized by a brittle behaviour with a relatively limited fracture energy. Recently, new types of adhesive with improved fracture toughness and ductility have been proposed. Among these, a two-component rubber-toughened epoxy adhesive was recently proposed for structural strengthening of steel elements. Preliminary studies showed that this adhesive has a fracture energy higher than that of standard adhesives (Meier et al., 2020)(Kasper et al., 2021)(Colombi et al., 2022), which allows for attaining higher CFRP-steel bond capacity. However, limited research is available on the behavior of CFRP-steel joints with toughened resin and it is mostly focused on the quasi-static response. The fatigue damage behavior of composites is still an open issue and different damage models have been proposed (Degrieck & Van Paepegem, 2001)(Ganesan et al., 2021). Among them, phenomenological models for residual stiffness or strength can capture the gradual damage evolution in terms of macroscopically observable properties (Shiri et al., 2015)(Llobet et al., 2017).

Within this framework, this work presents the preliminary results of an experimental and numerical investigation of the bond behavior of CFRP-steel joints bonded with a toughened adhesive and subjected to fatigue loading. Single-lap direct shear tests were conducted under both monotonic and cyclic loadings. Moreover, tensile fatigue tests of CFRP laminate rectangular coupons were conducted. The overall fatigue degradation of the strengthened system is numerically modelled by considering separately the damage occurring at the bonded interface and in the composite material. In particular, the interface behavior of the adhesively bonded joint is described by adopting a cohesive model, while the fiber-reinforced composite is described by adopting a fatigue residual stiffness model. The experimental results obtained are presented and employed to calibrate the parameters of the numerical models proposed. A parametric analysis is then carried out to investigate the effect of the main design parameters on the system response, considering situations that could be affected by the composite fatigue response.

DAMAGE MODELS

This section presents the numerical models proposed to describe the interfacial debonding failure under fatigue loading. A new damage-based cyclic cohesive zone model is proposed to characterize the interfacial shear behavior of the bonded joint. This model is based on a bond-slip law that relates the local interfacial shear stress to the corresponding slip. The adoption of an accurate bond-slip law is a key aspect for the correct representation of the system response. Then, a fatigue residual stiffness model characterized by a macroscopic reduction of the stiffness is adopted to describe the CFRP fatigue behavior. The macroscopic description of the fatigue phenomenon, through the evaluation of the stiffness reduction factor, represents a simple approach to investigate the influence of the composite fatigue behavior on the global system response of the bonded joint, without modelling the actual damage mechanisms occurring in the composite material.

The numerical analyses are performed by using an in-house finite element solver developed in MATLAB, with the material models and the cohesive zone model formulation embedded into a finite element framework. A one-dimensional model is adopted to represent single-lap direct shear tests, considering a pure Mode-II fracture mechanics loading condition. In particular, the adhesive behavior is described by cohesive elements with zero thickness and whose behavior is governed by the introduced bond-slip relationship.

Bond-slip model formulation

The damage-based cyclic cohesive zone model originally proposed in (Bocciarelli, 2021) for monotonic and cyclic loading is adopted in this study. The interface behavior under monotonic loading is governed by the definition of a free energy potential, with an exponentially decaying softening curve (Figure 1). The possible extension to cyclic loading conditions is performed by introducing a scalar damage variable, k , with a phenomenological rate equation governing its evolution in time, leading to a degrading stiffness and strength under cyclic loading.

Figure 1. Exponential bond-slip relationship.

The monotonic response is governed by the free energy potential Φ (Rose et al., 1981):

$$\Phi(\delta) = e\sigma_c\delta_c \left[1 - \left(1 + \frac{\delta}{\delta_c} \right) e^{-\delta/\delta_c} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where σ_c represents the cohesive law traction peak, δ_c the corresponding critical displacement. With η a non-dimensional parameter coupling the normal (indicated with the subscript n) and shear (indicated with the subscript s) behaviors, the scalar effective opening displacement δ is:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\delta_n^2 + \eta^2 \delta_s^2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The monotonic traction-separation law reads as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \end{bmatrix} = F(k) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \delta_n \\ \eta^2 \delta_s \end{bmatrix} \leq \begin{bmatrix} t_n^{lim} \\ t_s^{lim} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where t_n and t_s represent the normal and shear traction components, respectively, δ_n and δ_s represent the normal and shear components of the discontinuity displacement vector along the interface, respectively, and t_n^{lim} and t_s^{lim} are the maximum traction vector components transferred along the interface as function of δ and derived as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} t_n^{lim} \\ t_s^{lim} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial\Phi/\partial\delta_n \\ \partial\Phi/\partial\delta_s \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial\delta} \begin{bmatrix} \partial\Phi/\partial\delta_n \\ \partial\Phi/\partial\delta_s \end{bmatrix} = \frac{t^{lim}}{\delta} \begin{bmatrix} \delta_n \\ \eta^2 \delta_s \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where t^{lim} indicates an effective scalar measure of the maximum interface traction vector that can be transferred through the interface, defined as follows:

$$t^{lim} = \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial\delta} = \frac{\sigma_c}{\delta_c} e^{(1-\delta/\delta_c)} \delta \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

This equation represents the monotonic bond-slip response of the model.

To extend this law to cyclic debonding processes, linear damaging radial paths from the origin to the maximum attainable interface traction t^{lim} are assumed as per $t=F(k)\delta < t^{lim}(k)$. In Eq. 3, $F(k)$ is a degrading stiffness function of the damage variable k , defined as:

$$F(k) = \frac{\sigma_c}{\delta_c} e^{(1-\tilde{\delta}(k)/\delta_c)} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where $\tilde{\delta}(k)$ is a fictitious displacement governing the evolution of the damage variable k according to:

$$k = \left[1 - \left(1 + \frac{\tilde{\delta}}{\delta_c} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\tilde{\delta}}{\delta_c} \right)^2 \right) e^{-\tilde{\delta}/\delta_c} \right]^\lambda \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where λ is a model parameter affecting the damage evolution. This effective fictitious displacement must satisfy the following conditions: equal to zero when k equal to zero and equal to infinite when k equal to 1. The damage variable k can assume values between 0, indicating no damage, to 1, indicating complete failure, respectively. Material softening starts at peak point (σ_c, δ_c) and ends at complete failure with damage variable k equal to 1 and the traction value equal to 0.

For a monotonic loading path, the ascending/descending bond-slip curve is followed, according to Eqs. 4 and 5. Following the monotonic descending branch, the evolution of k is a function of the current opening displacement only. In this case, the scalar damage variable k is endowed of a physical interpretation. It indicates the energy dissipated up to the actual maximum effective displacement attained divided by the total fracture energy of the interface.

A different situation occurs during un- and re-loading cycles, fundamental to describe fatigue-driven debonding behavior. For cyclic loading, the evolution of the damage parameter k is governed by the following equations:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{k} = \hat{\alpha}k[t - \beta t^{lim}(k)]\dot{\delta} & \text{if } [t - \beta t^{lim}]\dot{\delta} > 0 \\ \dot{k} = 0 & [t - \beta t^{lim}]\dot{\delta} < 0 \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

with $\hat{\alpha} = \alpha$ for $\dot{\delta} > 0$ and $\hat{\alpha} = -\gamma$ for $\dot{\delta} < 0$ and where the upper dot denotes the corresponding rate quantity. According to Eq. 8, during un- and re-loading cycles the following alternatives hold:

- Initial unloading stage: $\dot{\delta} < 0$ and $t > \beta t^{lim}$; then, $[t - \beta t^{lim}]\dot{\delta} < 0$ and $\dot{k} = 0$, which means no damage evolution.
- Final unloading stage: $\dot{\delta} < 0$ and $t < \beta t^{lim}$; then, $[t - \beta t^{lim}]\dot{\delta} > 0$ and $\dot{k} = -\gamma k[t - \beta t^{lim}]\dot{\delta} < 0$, which means damage healing or crack retardation.
- Initial reloading stage: $\dot{\delta} > 0$ and $t < \beta t^{lim}$; then, $[t - \beta t^{lim}]\dot{\delta} < 0$ and $\dot{k} = 0$, which means no damage evolution.
- Final reloading stage: $\dot{\delta} > 0$ and $t > \beta t^{lim}$; then, $[t - \beta t^{lim}]\dot{\delta} > 0$ and $\dot{k} = \alpha k[t - \beta t^{lim}]\dot{\delta} > 0$, which means damage incrementation.

Following the monotonic descending branch, the evolution of k is a function of the current opening displacement only, while considering un- and re-loading cycles, the damage evolution depends on the rate of deformation, previous damage accumulation, cohesive traction, and fatigue threshold indicated as βt^{lim} . A new set of model parameters, namely α , β and γ , is introduced in Eq. 8. These parameters govern the cyclic response behavior and are then referred to as fatigue parameters. In particular, α represents the rate of damage accumulation during loading, while γ represents the rate of damage reduction (crack healing) during the un-loading cycle phase. Finally, β governs the fatigue threshold in loading and un-loading and is smaller than 1. Another model parameter affecting damage evolution is represented by λ . A smaller λ induces a greater amount of damage accumulated at the beginning due to crack initiation.

An important aspect is represented by the different definition of damage evolution during cyclic loadings. In particular, both the loading and un-loading phases are divided into two steps governed by the set of fatigue parameters. In the first step, the damage variable k is kept constant, while in the

second step the damage variable evolves, either increasing or decreasing in loading and un-loading, respectively.

One important feature of the model is the ability to incorporate also crack initiation, where generally a major part of fatigue life is spent (Anderson, 2017). Therefore, the model does not present an initial linear elastic branch and damage starts to accumulate as soon as the effective jump displacement is different from zero. Finally, crack arrest can be represented by a compensation at each loading and un-loading cycle between damage healing and incrementation, respectively.

Composite residual stiffness model

Generally, in fiber-reinforced composites fatigue damage is a quite complex phenomenon. These materials present an anisotropic and heterogeneous behavior, with different types of damage mechanisms interacting among them (Degrieck & Van Paepegem, 2001). Based on the experimental outcomes, the fatigue damage process can be divided into three main stages of stiffness degradation: rapid initial decline, linear gradual reduction, and final rupture. Different fatigue failure models have been proposed in the literature and they can be classified into three main categories: fatigue life models not considering the actual degradation mechanisms but using S-N curves or Goodman-type diagrams; phenomenological models for residual stiffness or strength representation; and progressive damage models using damage variables related to measurable manifestation of damage. The second class of models represents a suitable choice for the material description in this study. The phenomenological models introduce an evolution law describing the gradual degradation of stiffness or strength in terms of macroscopically observable properties. Residual stiffness models consider the deterioration of stiffness due to fatigue loading. Stiffness can be measured frequently and with non-destructive methods. In this work, a residual stiffness model originally proposed in (Van Paepegem & Degrieck, 2002) is adopted. It introduces a measure of the stiffness loss expressed by two different terms (initiation and propagation) and it also introduces a modified static failure criterion representing the decreasing ultimate static strength. The model is one-dimensional, considering only the longitudinal stiffness in the loading direction. The scalar damage variable D is a macroscopic index of the fatigue damage and is defined as:

$$D = 1 - \frac{E}{E_0} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where E_0 is the stiffness of the non-damaged homogenized material, while E represents the current stiffness. In this framework, the damage growth law proposed is:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = f_i(\sigma, D) + f_p(\sigma, D) \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

The damage growth law represents the damage increment per cycle N . The function f_i describes the first stage of damage initiation, while f_p describes the following gradual damage propagation and final rupture. The damage initiation and damage propagation functions are:

$$f_i = c_1 \Sigma(\sigma, D) \exp\left(-c_2 \frac{D}{\sqrt{\Sigma(\sigma, D)}}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$$f_p = c_3 D \Sigma(\sigma, D)^2 \left[1 + \exp(c_5 (\Sigma(\sigma, D) - c_4))\right] \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

where $\Sigma(\sigma, D)$ is the fatigue failure index, defined as $1/R$, with R being the calculated safety factor from the Tsai-Wu static failure criterion:

$$\Sigma(\sigma, D) = \frac{1}{R} = \frac{\tilde{\sigma}}{X} = \frac{\sigma}{X(1-D)} = \frac{E_0 \varepsilon}{X} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

with ε indicating the strain and X the static strength, respectively, while $\tilde{\sigma}$ represents the effective stress. Eq. 13 shows that Σ expresses a ratio between the effective stress and corresponding strength. Five different material parameters are present in the model and called c_i ($i=1, \dots, 5$). The first two affect the damage initiation phase, while the remaining three the damage propagation phase. In

particular: the constant c_1 represents the damage initiation rate, while the exponential function depends on the damage D and constant c_2 associated with the saturating damage level. Then, c_3 is the damage propagation rate, c_4 is a stress threshold below which no fiber fracture occurs and once this threshold is crossed the exponential function increases the damage evolution very fast leading to final failure according to c_5 .

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

This section presents the preliminary results of an ongoing experimental campaign performed at the Material Testing Laboratory of the Politecnico di Milano, aimed at investigating the tensile and bond behavior of a CFRP pultruded composite under fatigue loading. Three CFRP rectangular coupons were tested under tensile fatigue loading to investigate the effect of different cyclic actions on the composite material. Besides, single-lap direct shear tests were performed on six CFRP-steel joints, three tested under quasi-static monotonic loading and the other three under cyclic loading up to failure. The results of the static tests are not discussed in this paper for brevity. However, their average ultimate load, $P_u=31.17$ kN (CoV=2.70%), was adopted as a reference value for the fatigue cyclic load range. The specimens were named following the notation DS(or T)_L_n, where DS(=direct shear) or T(=tensile) indicates the test type, L indicates the loading scheme where M(=monotonic) or F(=fatigue), and n is the specimen number.

Table 1: Material properties

Mechanical properties	CFRP	Steel	Adhesive
Elastic modulus	$E_p=210$ GPa [□]	$E_{st}=210$ GPa [□]	$E_a= 3.65$ GPa
Yield stress	-	$\sigma_y = 275$ MPa [□]	-
Tensile strength	$\sigma_{p,u}=3200$ MPa [□]	$\sigma_{st,u}=430$ MPa [□]	$\sigma_{a,u}= 21$ MPa
Ultimate tensile strain	$\varepsilon_{p,u}>1.80\%$ [□]	$\varepsilon_{st,u}=15$ % [□]	$\varepsilon_{a,u}=1.35\%$

Note: [□] declared by the manufacturer.

Tensile fatigue tests on CFRP

Three tensile fatigue tests on unidirectional CFRP composite coupons were performed (Figure 2a). The pultruded CFRP plate had a 0.68 carbon fiber volume fraction and mechanical properties reported in Table 1 as declared by the manufacturer (Sika Italia S.p.A., 2019). Specimens were cut from a 100 mm wide composite laminate and their width, thickness and length were $b_p=20$ mm, $t_p=1.4$ mm, and $L=200$ mm. The coupon ends were reinforced with epoxy bonded GFRP tabs to promote a uniform distribution of the machine clamping pressure during the test.

Specimens were initially subjected to a displacement-controlled loading ramp, until the average fatigue load was attained. Then, the control was switched in force mode and a sinusoidal load ranging between P_{max} and P_{min} (see Table 2) was applied to the specimen with a frequency of 6 Hz. A target number of 1 million cycles was adopted. A strain gauge sensor with a gauge length of 20 mm was bonded to the middle of the specimen to measure its axial strain throughout the test and detect possible material degradation.

Table 2: Cyclic load values in fatigue tests

Specimen	P_{max} [kN]	P_{min} [kN]	Load ratio R [-]	N_f [$\times 10^3$]	Specimen	P_{max} [kN]	P_{min} [kN]	Load ratio R [-]	N_f [$\times 10^3$]
T_F_1	20.13	10.07	0.50	462	DS_F_1	20.13	10.07	0.50	244
T_F_2	47.04	36.98	0.79	1140	DS_F_2				228
T_F_3	62.72	52.66	0.84	1170	DS_F_3				191

Figure 2: Experimental tests: (a) tensile fatigue test on a CFRP coupon; and (b) single-lap direct shear test on a CFRP-steel joint

Direct shear tests on CFRP-steel joints

The specimen comprised a CFRP laminate bonded to the flange of a HEB100 standard steel profile (steel class S275) by using a newly developed rubber-toughened epoxy adhesive (Sika AG, 2022). The declared mechanical properties of the steel substrate are reported in Table 1. The mechanical properties of the adhesive were obtained by performing tensile tests on dog-bone shaped specimens. Details on the toughening process and adhesive characterization can be found in (Kasper et al., 2021). Figure 2b shows the single-lap direct shear test setup adopted in the present study. The suitability of this test methodology to investigate the CFRP-to-steel bonded joint response considering a pure Mode-II loading condition is well established in the literature (Xia & Teng, 2005)(Yuan et al., 2004). The HEB100 steel profile had a length of 250 mm, whereas the flange thickness and width were $t_{st}=10$ mm and $b_{st}=100$ mm, respectively. The composite plate width, thickness, and bonded length were $b_p=20$ mm, $t_p=1.4$ mm, and $L=200$ mm. The plate loaded end was set 20 mm far from the substrate edge to prevent any wedge effect. The plate was left unbonded for 200 mm at the loaded end side and was equipped with epoxy bonded GFRP tabs to promote a uniform distribution of the machine clamping pressure. A rigid frame made of steel plates and threaded rods was used to restrain the specimen to the bottom head of a servo-hydraulic universal testing machine equipped with a 250 kN load cell. Tests were conducted in quasi-static displacement-control mode, at a stroke rate of 0.05 mm/min. In the case of fatigue cyclic loading, each specimen was first loaded in quasi-static displacement-control mode, at a rate of 0.05 mm/min, until the maximum fatigue load P_{max} was reached. Then, the applied load was decreased with the same rate until the average fatigue load was reached. Subsequently, a constant amplitude sinusoidal load ($P_{max}=0.65P_u$; $P_{min}=0.32P_u$) was applied in force-control mode with a frequency of 6 Hz until failure.

Two LVDT sensors, bonded to the steel support and reacting off of an L-shaped plate attached to the composite plate loaded end, were adopted to measure the relative displacement between the two adherends at the loaded end.

Test results and discussion

The CFRP coupons tested in tension T_F_1 and T_F_2 did not show any significant degradation during the loading cycles, while specimen T_F_3, which was subjected to a higher load, showed a progression of damage, although limited. This variation in normalized stiffness (E/E_0) with respect to the number of cycles (N) was then considered for the numerical modelling. In this work, the main aim of the tests performed on CFRP composite was to characterize the material degradation when subjected to cyclic loadings to investigate its possible influence on the global behavior of the CFRP-steel joint. Further studies could investigate the influence of various parameters involved, such as the stress ratio, size effect, fiber orientation, and others.

All DS specimens showed a cohesive failure within the adhesive layer. The axial stress-global slip curves were obtained (see Figure 3a), where the axial stress $\sigma = P/A_p$ is the ratio between the applied load P and the CFRP plate cross-sectional area $A_p = b_p t_p$, whereas the global slip g is the average reading of the two LVDT sensors. Figure 3a features the initial displacement-controlled ramp of the σ - g response, the subsequent descending ramp from P_{\max} to the average fatigue load, 10-cycle blocks extracted each 25000 cycles, and the final loading cycles that led to failure of specimen DS_F_2. The specimen stiffness was evaluated as the slope of the secant line joining peak and valley of each cycle and its reduction with the number of cycles was regarded as a damage propagation within the bonded interface. The un-loading path does not clearly coincide with the loading path, indicating hysteresis under each cycle due to the fracture energy release. The progressive reduction of the stiffness due to the propagation of debonding along the joint length significantly increases as the number of cycles approaches the failure. A sudden collapse occurred, due to the full propagation of the cohesive crack in the adhesive, once the residual bonded length was no longer sufficient to transfer the applied load from the strip to the substrate. The response of the tested specimens was consistent, with a number of cycles at failure ranging between approximately 240,000 and 190,000 (see Table 2). The propagation of the cohesive crack from the loaded end towards the free end of the specimen was gradual. The debonding started at the loaded end of the composite plate, although the applied maximum load was smaller than the static peak load. Then, debonding propagated towards the free end with the increasing of applied load cycles. The adhesive adopted exhibited a large energy absorption with a pronounced ductile behavior and ultimate strain. These characteristics can be attributed to the use of a toughened adhesive.

Figure 3: Comparison between experimental and numerical results: (a) axial stress-global slip curve of specimen DS_F_2; (b) normalized stiffness of CFRP composite specimen T_F_3

NUMERICAL STUDY

This section presents the preliminary results obtained from the numerical modelling of the experimental tests. Based on experimental evidence, it is generally assumed that the interface of a single-lap shear test is mainly subjected to Mode-II loading condition and therefore a one-dimensional model is suitable to describe its behavior. In this model, the substrate was considered rigid while the CFRP plate and interfacial behavior were governed by the fatigue damage models presented above. The interface was modelled by cohesive elements with zero thickness. The analyses were developed with an in-house finite element solver implemented in MATLAB. First, the parameters of the two models were calibrated separately based on the experimental results. Then, a numerical parametric analysis was developed to investigate possible configurations where the CFRP fatigue damage can become significant.

Calibration

The bond-slip law was calibrated from the results of quasi-static monotonic specimens, which provided the peak shear stress $\tau_{\max} = \sigma_c = 17.63$ MPa (see Figure 1a) and fracture energy $G_f = 4.05$ N/mm. The fatigue parameters $\alpha = 0.2483$, $\beta = 0.625$, $\gamma = 0.0$, and $\lambda = 0.60$ were identified based on the results of the specimens tested with cyclic loading. In this first case, the composite strip was considered as linear elastic with no influence of the fatigue loading on the mechanical properties. In Figure 3a, the experimental results, and corresponding predicted responses for specimen DS_F_2, are compared in

terms of axial stress versus global slip. Experimental and numerical results are consistent in terms of overall response and number of cycles at failure.

The parameters of the model describing the composite fatigue behavior were identified based on the results of specimen T_F_3. Since eventual rupture of the specimens did not occur, only the first three model parameters were calibrated, i.e., c_1 , c_2 , c_3 , which describe the initial degradation of material properties and the damage propagation. The calibrated parameters were $c_1=0.5e-04$, $c_2=50$, and $c_3=1.0e-012$. Figure 3b shows the normalized stiffness for specimen T_F_3 which was accurately captured by the numerical model with the c_i parameters calibrated.

Results and parametric analysis

The parameters calibrated were then employed to study the behavior of single-lap direct shear test specimens subjected to fatigue loading, modeling the CFRP composite with the fatigue damage model. The numerical responses of the direct shear test obtained considering the CFRP composite as elastic or accounting for the fatigue damage are compared in Figure 4. Figure 4 shows that the introduction of the composite damage model did not influence the global slip at failure of the joint, while it slightly reduced (approximately 3%) the number of cycles at failure. This behavior can be attributed to the load values applied during the fatigue test that were rather low with respect to those observed to affect the tensile fatigue behavior of CFRP coupons.

Figure 4: Comparison between axial stress-global slip curves obtained considering elastic and damaging composite

For this reason, a numerical parametric analysis was performed to investigate system configurations that could be affected by CFRP damage. Parametric analyses were performed by varying the thickness t_p and the elastic modulus E_p of the composite plate, while the cohesive and CFRP damage model parameters calibrated above were adopted. Three values for each parameter were considered, maintaining the other as fixed, namely $t_p=1.2, 1.4, 1.8$ mm, and $E_p=150, 190, 225$ GPa. Three different load levels were considered, expressed as the ratio between the fatigue load applied and the joint capacity (Xia & Teng, 2005), namely 65%, 70%, and 80%. The CFRP was considered either elastic or fatigue damage was accounted for.

Figure 5 and Table 3 provide the results for the different parameter combinations considered. The variation of the composite properties affects the joint capacity (Xia & Teng, 2005) and consequently the load applied. Namely, the joint capacity is directly proportional to the elastic modulus and inversely proportional to the thickness (Xia & Teng, 2005). In Table 3, the difference of the number of cycles at failure between corresponding simulations with elastic and damaging composite is reported. The results obtained showed that damage in the composite had a larger influence in the system response when many loading cycles are required to reach the failure, even if the ratio between the load applied and the joint capacity is lower. A maximum difference of approximately 13% was obtained in the number of cycles at failure between model with and without damaging CFRP composite (Table 3).

Table 3: Results of the parametric analysis in terms of difference of number of cycles at failure obtained numerically, Δ , and damage in the composite D (Eq. 9)

Parameter		E_p [GPa] ($t_p=1.4$ mm)			t_p [mm] ($E_p=190$ GPa)		
Value		150	190	225	1.2	1.4	1.8
Δ (%)	80%	0.26	0.31	0.36	0.55	0.31	0.00
	70%	2.07	2.00	2.04	2.34	2.00	1.51
	65%	12.43	11.67	10.76	13.45	11.67	8.62
Damage D (%)	80%	0.56	0.54	0.52	0.64	0.54	0.40
	70%	1.31	1.28	1.25	1.46	1.28	1.01
	65%	2.34	2.30	2.26	2.57	2.30	1.88

Figure 5: Difference of the number of cycles at failure between elastic and damaging composite at different load levels and varying: (a) the elastic modulus and (b) the thickness of the composite plate.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, preliminary results of an experimental and numerical investigation on the bond behavior of CFRP-to-steel joints under fatigue loading were presented. Single-lap cyclic direct shear tests on bonded joints and tensile fatigue tests on the composite material were performed and then used to calibrate the numerical model proposed to describe damage initiation and propagation in the bonded interface and in the CFRP. A new approach that separately considers the fatigue behavior of the bonded joint and of the composite material was considered. The interface behavior of the adhesively bonded joint was modeled by an exponential damaging bond-slip relationship, while the composite plate was described by adopting a fatigue residual stiffness model. Preliminary results of a numerical parametric analysis aimed at investigating possible critical configurations were presented. The results obtained through the numerical models highlighted in particular the influence of the composite damage on the number of cycles at failure. Future work will include further experimental and numerical results to investigate adhesives and composites with different properties and performances to extend the parametric investigation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The experimental tests were conducted at the Laboratorio Prove Materiali of the Politecnico di Milano, Italy. Sika Services AG, Zurich, is gratefully acknowledged for providing the composites and resins.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

Anderson, T. L. (2017). *Fracture Mechanics: Fundamental and Applications*. CRC Press.

- Bocciarelli, M. (2021). A new cohesive law for the simulation of crack propagation under cyclic loading. Application to steel- and concrete-FRP bonded interface. *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, 114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tafmec.2021.102992>
- Bocciarelli, M., Colombi, P., Fava, G., & Poggi, C. (2007). Interaction of interface delamination and plasticity in tensile steel members reinforced by CFRP plates. *International Journal of Fracture*, 146(1–2), 79–92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10704-007-9144-8>
- Bocciarelli, M., Colombi, P., Fava, G., & Poggi, C. (2009). Prediction of debonding strength of tensile steel/CFRP joints using fracture mechanics and stress based criteria. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 76(2), 299–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2008.10.005>
- Borrie, D., Al-saadi, S., Zhao, X. L., Singh Raman, R. K., & Bai, Y. (2021). Bonded cfrp/steel systems, remedies of bond degradation and behaviour of CFRP repaired steel: An overview. In *Polymers* (Vol. 13, Issue 9). MDPI AG. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13091533>
- Carrara, P., & De Lorenzis, L. (2015). A coupled damage-plasticity model for the cyclic behavior of shear-loaded interfaces. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, 85, 33–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmps.2015.09.002>
- Colombi, P., & Fava, G. (2012). Fatigue behaviour of tensile steel/CFRP joints. *Composite Structures*, 94(8), 2407–2417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.03.001>
- Colombi, P., & Fava, G. (2015). Experimental study on the fatigue behaviour of cracked steel beams repaired with CFRP plates. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 145, 128–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2015.04.009>
- Cruz, P., León, A. D. De, Wisniewski, D., & Valente, I. (2007). Sustainable Bridges Assessment for Future Traffic Demands and Longer Lives. In *Concrete*.
- Degrieck, J., & Van Paepegem, W. (2001). Fatigue Damage Modelling of Fibre-Reinforced Composite Materials. In *Review. Applied Mechanics Reviews* (Vol. 54, Issue 4).
- Domazet, Z. (1996). Comparison of fatigue crack retardation methods. *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 3(2), 137–147. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1350-6307\(96\)00006-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/1350-6307(96)00006-4)
- Doroudi, Y., Fernando, D., Nguyen, V. T., & Torres, J. P. (2019). Experimental Study on CFRP-to-Steel Bonded Interfaces under Quasi-Static Cyclic Loading. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 23(4). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)cc.1943-5614.0000945](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)cc.1943-5614.0000945)
- Doroudi, Y., Fernando, D., Zhou, H., Nguyen, V. T., & Ghafoori, E. (2020). Fatigue behavior of FRP-to-steel bonded interface: An experimental study with a damage plasticity model. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2020.105785>
- Fernando, D., Yu, T., & Teng, J. G. (2014). Behavior of CFRP Laminates Bonded to a Steel Substrate Using a Ductile Adhesive. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 18(2). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)cc.1943-5614.0000439](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)cc.1943-5614.0000439)
- Ganesan, C., Joanna, P. S., & Singh, D. (2021). Fatigue life modeling of FRP composites: A comprehensive review. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 46, 555–561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.11.119>
- Ghafoori, E., Motavalli, M., Zhao, X. L., Nussbaumer, A., & Fontana, M. (2015). Fatigue design criteria for strengthening metallic beams with bonded CFRP plates. *Engineering Structures*, 101, 542–557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2015.07.048>
- Jiang, C., Yu, Q. Q., & Gu, X. L. (2021). A unified bond-slip model for the interface between FRP and steel. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2021.109380>
- Kasper, Y., Albiez, M., Ummenhofer, T., Mayer, C., Meier, T., Choffat, F., Ciupack, Y., & Pasternak, H. (2021). Application of toughened epoxy-adhesives for strengthening of fatigue-damaged steel structures. *Construction and Building Materials*, 275, 121579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.121579>
- Liu, H. B., Zhao, X. L., & Al-Mahaidi, R. (2010). Effect of fatigue loading on bond strength between CFRP sheets and steel plates. *International Journal of Structural Stability and Dynamics*, 10(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219455410003348>
- Llobet, J., Maimí, P., Mayugo, J. A., Essa, Y., & Martin de la Escalera, F. (2017). A fatigue damage and residual strength model for unidirectional carbon/epoxy composites under on-axis tension-tension loadings. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 103, 508–515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2017.06.026>

- Martinelli, E., & Caggiano, A. (2014). A unified theoretical model for the monotonic and cyclic response of FRP strips glued to concrete. *Polymers*, 6(1), 370–381.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/polym6020370>
- Meier, T., Choffat, F., & Montalbano, A. (2020). Toughened 2K-epoxy adhesives: Structural strengthening of steel structures. *IABSE Congress, Christchurch 2020: Resilient Technologies for Sustainable Infrastructure - Proceedings*, 898–902.
<https://doi.org/10.2749/christchurch.2021.0898>
- Rose, J. H., Ferrante, J., & Smith, J. R. (1981). Universal binding energy curves for metals and bimetallic interfaces. *Physical Review Letters*, 47(9), 675–678.
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.47.675>
- Schijve, J. (2003). Fatigue of structures and materials in the 20th century and the state of the art. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 25(8), 679–702. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-1123\(03\)00051-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-1123(03)00051-3)
- Shiri, S., Yazdani, M., & Pourgol-Mohammad, M. (2015). A fatigue damage accumulation model based on stiffness degradation of composite materials. *Materials and Design*, 88, 1290–1295.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2015.09.114>
- Sika AG. (n.d.). Sikadur-370 Scheda Dati Prodotto. In 2022. Retrieved December 10, 2022, from <https://www.sika.com/en/innovation/sika-innovation-flash/pioneering-steel-bridge-repair--sikadur--370.html>
- Sika Italia S.p.A. (2019). *Sika CarboDur M614(IT) Scheda Dati Prodotto*.
- Täljsten, B., Hansen, C. S., & Schmidt, J. W. (2009). Strengthening of old metallic structures in fatigue with prestressed and non-prestressed CFRP laminates. *Construction and Building Materials*, 23(4), 1665–1677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2008.08.001>
- Teng, J. G., Yu, T., & Fernando, D. (2012). Strengthening of steel structures with fiber-reinforced polymer composites. In *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* (Vol. 78, pp. 131–143). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2012.06.011>
- Van Paepegem, W., & Degrieck, J. (2002). A New Coupled Approach of Residual Stiffness and Strength for Fatigue of Fibre-reinforced Composites. In *International Journal of Fatigue* (Vol. 24, Issue 7).
- Wang, H. T., Wu, G., Pang, Y. Y., Shi, J. W., & Zakari, H. M. (2019). Experimental study on the bond behavior between CFRP plates and steel substrates under fatigue loading. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.107266>
- Xia, S. H., & Teng, J. G. (2005). Behaviour of FRP-to-steel bonded joints. *Proceedings of the International Symposium on Bond Behaviour of FRP in Structures, BBFS 2005*, 411–418.
- Yu, T., Fernando, D., Teng, J. G., & Zhao, X. L. (2012). Experimental study on CFRP-to-steel bonded interfaces. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 43(5), 2279–2289.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2012.01.024>
- Yuan, H., Teng, J. G., Seracino, R., Wu, Z. S., & Yao, J. (2004). Full-range behavior of FRP-to-concrete bonded joints. *Engineering Structures*, 26(5), 553–565.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2003.11.006>
- Zhao, X. L. (2013). *FRP strengthened metallic structures*. CRC Press.